

A woman wearing a wide-brimmed hat is shown in profile, looking down at a plant in a field. She is holding a small white tag with a QR code. The background is a vast field of crops under a blue sky. The entire image has a blue tint and a large white curved shape on the right side.

GENDER-RESPONSIVE CROP BREEDING:

COLLECTING GENDER-DISAGGREGATED TRAIT PREFERENCE DATA

Demonstrations
Head to Head Trials
Varietal Cafeteria
Participatory Varietal Selection

GENDER
Platform

IRRI

Traditionally, breeding programs have developed varieties suitable for specific agro-ecological conditions. This has been embellished with taking into consideration the crop management regimes. However, it has been recognized that we need to not just breed for places, but for people who will be using those varieties.

Demand-led breeding is important to ensure that the products developed are consistent with the demands, needs, and preferences of farmers, consumers and processors. Higher relevance is expected to lead to higher adoption, and consequently wider impact.

Understanding gender-differentiated trait preferences of various actors is critical to inform demand-led breeding priorities and investment decisions. The sets of traits that different socio-economic groups/customer segments, spanning producers, consumers, millers, traders and other value chain actors, desire in the rice varieties they grow and consume could be different (and different between women and men) within these groups. The aim is not to develop separate varieties for men and women, but to invest in developing varieties that include preferred traits of both women and men. We cannot breed for the large number of diverse traits that women and men prefer, but we can ensure the 'must have' traits for both are included. We also need to ensure that the not-so desirable traits which might affect women and men negatively are managed (e.g., requiring high labour or costs, etc).

A review of literature (across all crops, agro-ecologies and regions) concludes broadly that: (1) overall, men focus more on production and marketing-related traits; (2) while women focus on production and use (post harvest and food preparation) related traits.

However, when both groups face similar constraints (mostly production and agro-ecological), they tend to mention similar preferences. However, evidence is very sparse with regard to gender-differentiated trait preferences. Very few studies conducted and published focused on Asia (13%) and fewer on rice.

WOMEN'S TRAIT PREFERENCES SEEM TO BE:

- **Based on their roles on the farm and in the household (e.g, yield, cooking quality, ease of manual threshing, straw quality and quantity, storability, grain characteristics, losses, by-products)**
- **Related to family food security (earliness, multiple harvests, production in unfavourable conditions like bad years or poor soils)**
- **Production goals (either producing for home consumption or market)**
- **Based on their resource access (e.g, land holding, labour availability)**

Available data also indicates that in addition to gender, Intersectional factors like poverty, caste, and location (determines vulnerability due to abiotic stresses faced) influence trait preferences. So also do other factors like land holding size, production purpose, family labour participation, access to information, social networks and, intra-household decision making. Preferences also tend to vary with changes in agro-ecologies induced by climate change and other socio-economic, market, and policy forces. It is, therefore, important to capture these trait preferences on a continuous basis to inform breeding investments. Periodic surveys are one way of generating this data, but often research programs do not have adequate resources to conduct large-scale surveys on a regular basis. Therefore, we need to look for cost-effective ways of generating this data.

In this regard, regular activities that are conducted by research and development organizations such as demonstrations, field days, crops cafeterias and Participatory Varietal Selection (PVS) become important. While information on varietal choices is collected during these events, gender-disaggregated information is not. They also stop short at asking for choices, but not the reason behind those choices. It is important to understand these reasons as that will determine if and what breeding solutions might be appropriate.

MIXED-METHODS TOOL KIT This toolkit provides formats for collecting gender-disaggregated trait preference data conducted regularly:

- **Demonstrations**
- **Head to Head Trials**
- **Varietal cafeteria**
- **Participatory Varietal Selection**

GENERATING GENDER-DISAGGREGATED VARIETAL TRAIT PREFERENCE DATA

Template for data collection during field days related to Demonstrations and Head to Head Trials

DEMONSTRATIONS

Varietal demonstrations provide opportunities for farmers and other stakeholders to become aware of new crop varieties and also evaluate the varieties for the features they like or not. Agro-ecologically appropriate crop varieties are cultivated on farmer fields and the demonstrations are managed by participating farmers or farmer groups. Participating and nonparticipating farmers can observe performance of different new varieties. The demonstrations are designed to enhance awareness of new varieties along with acquiring knowledge regarding their management practices and benefits. This is expected to positively influence adoption of the new varieties and contribute varietal replacement.

FIELD DAYS

Field days are organized in the context of both demonstrations and H2H Trials, where women and men farmers, researchers, extension agents, government officials and other public and private rice value chain actors are invited to witness the performance of the new varieties grown and evaluate the varieties using the criteria they deem important. Field days are held once or twice during the crop growing season, particularly just before harvest. Field days provide an opportunity to gather preferences of women and men with regard to the traits they observe and seek in a new crop variety.

In a departure from traditional data that is collected, the formats provided here include additional demographic data and allow collection of sex-disaggregated data during field days. They also include questions to

HEAD TO HEAD (H2H) TRIALS

In a head-to-head trial, a new rice variety and a traditional variety are grown side by side in the same plot. This provides participating farmers with an opportunity to observe and compare the performance of these two varieties. Since the management practices for both varieties are the same, any advantage gained (yield, grain quality, etc.) can be attributed to the new variety. This method is simple and allows targeting individual farmers intensively, thus enabling them to observe, compare, and decide on two demonstrated varieties in their own field conditions.

understand why a certain person or group prefers certain traits in a crop variety and not just what they prefer. However, they need to be brief as interacting with all the people visiting the demonstrations might not be possible and they might not have the time to engage for long discussions. Alternatively, if feasible, sex-disaggregated stakeholder focus group discussions might be organized to collect this information. If collected regularly and systematically when field days are organized and analysed critically, they provide important insights into gender-disaggregated trait preferences. This helps in developing appropriate breeding solutions. This helps fill a key evidence gap and also allow to continuously generate such data with minimal costs.

DATA COLLECTION FORMAT

Guide to the questionnaire

A. General and demographic information

- Date
- Start time
- End time
- Name of supervising officer
- Job title of supervising officer
- Contact details of supervising officer (Phone number and/or email address)
- If event is hosted by another organisation, indicate name (and other relevant geographical details)
- Country
- Region
- District
- Village
- Ward/Block/any other place description
- Name of the Farmer
- Gender (F/M)
- Ethnicity/caste (if sensitive, do not ask)
- Age (years)
- Mobile no.
- Highest education level (1=none; 2=primary; 3=secondary; 4=higher)
- Years of engagement in farming
- Marital status (1=currently married/monogamous; 2= currently married/polygamous; 3=widowed; 4=divorced; 5=single)
- Size of land owned (acres)
- GPS coordinates (if applicable) - N1, E1, N2, E2

B. Demonstration/trial details and Varietal Features and Performance

- Crop Cut Details (demonstration plots)
- Name of variety
- Planting system (direct seeding, transplanting, any other)
- Date of Sowing
- Date of Transplanting
- Date of Harvesting
- Whether Fertilizer Applied (Manure, Chemical, No)
- If any stress experienced during growing season (Flood, Drought, salinity, none) If yes, number of days
- No of life saving Irrigations
- % of loss due to disease/Pest affect (if any)
- No of tillers (average of Five Hills)

- No of grains (average of five Panicles)
- Grain type (eg long and slender etc)
- Height of plant (average of five plants)
- Total yield in 5X5 sq m. (in kg) (where applicable)
- Total yield (tonnes/hectare)

Feedback on varieties demonstrated in trials

- Participant name
- Stakeholder type (eg extension officer etc)
- Gender (F/M)
- Feedback on varieties demonstrated in trials
 - What are the 3 most important things you liked about this variety? Why?
 - What are the 3 things you did not like about this variety? Why?
 - What variety do you grow now?
 - What is the one feature in a new variety that will motivate you to switch from the old one?

Download templates here:
bit.ly/genderresponsivecropbreeding

VARIETAL CAFETERIA

Template for data collection during field days related to Varietal Cafeteria

A varietal cafeteria is a display of 15-20 agro-ecologically appropriate varieties of a particular crop in one large plot, replicated along with their checks. Farmers, representatives of departments of agriculture, seed producers, distributors and researchers are invited to observe and assess comparative performance of those varieties. This also provides an opportunity to understand why certain stakeholders prefer one variety over another, particularly in capturing gender-disaggregated preferences. This assessment helps in selecting varieties with significant advantages over others, in a particular ecology, so they can be promoted.

DATA COLLECTION FORMAT

Guide to the questionnaire

This questionnaire consists of three parts:

Part 1: Basic data

This comprises:

A. Basic details of the varieties displayed

- Date
- Start time
- End time
- Name of supervising officer
- Job title of supervising officer
- Contact details of supervising officer (Phone number and/or email address)
- Country
- Region
- District
- Village
- Station/Ward/Block/any other place description
- If event is hosted by another organisation, indicate name (and other relevant geographical details)

Part 2: Socio-economic data and cafeteria scorecard form

A. Farmers' data: contains basic socio-economic and demographic characteristics of the participating farmers

- Number code
- Sex (F/M)
- Ethnicity/caste (if sensitive, do not ask)
- Age (years)
- Household size
- Highest education level (1 - None, 2 - Primary, 3 - Secondary, 4 - Higher)
- Marital status (1 - currently married/monogamous, 2 - currently married/polygamous, 3 - widowed, 4 - divorced, 5 - single)
- Size of land owned (local unit, please specify)
- Rice area (acres)
- Number of years growing rice
- Produce utilization (Percentage sold, percentage saved, percentage given to others)

B. Individual cafeteria scorecard data evaluation form

Table 1

- Number code
- Sex (F/M)
- Age (years)
- Variety name
- Stress tolerance (Flood; Drought; Salinity; Flood+Drought)
- Time to maturity (No. of days, approximately; Suitable; Not Suitable)
- Crop height (Less, More)

Table 2

- Number code
- Sex (F/M)
- Age (years)
- Variety name
- Tillering ability (Acceptable, Not Acceptable, Normal)
- Grain milling quality/head rice recovery (Low, High, Normal)
- Grain Type (Type, Like, Dislike, Why)

Table 3

- Number code
- Sex (F/M)
- Age (years)
- Variety name
- Did you notice disease in the variety? (Yes/No)
- Did you notice pest/insect in the variety? (Yes/No)
- Expected yield (Less, More, Normal)
- Actual yield (tonnes/ha)
- Water requirement (Less, More, Normal)
- Rice variety score out of 5 (1=least preferred, 5=most preferred)

To enable parts (A) and (B) correspond to the same respondent during data collection, ensure same number code is used for parts (A) and (B), so that both parts of the results refer to the same person. To further ensure the entries are attributed to the same respondent, the first few column entries for parts (A) and (B) are similar

Part 3: Focus Group Discussions with separate men and women groups

These gender-specific FGDs are designed to elicit detailed qualitative information underlying varietal scores and preferences. Facilitators of FGDs need to:

- Aim for about 6-8 participants (keeping in mind the additional translation time in some contexts).
- To enhance a diversity of participants are invited, the pre-FGD participant registration form captures some socio-economic variation (which can be shared beforehand with personnel assisting with participant engagement)
- Please ensure timeslots when men and women are invited to participate are when their other time demands are likely to be lower, according

to the local area norms (eg in most rural areas, most women farmers may be more available after mid-morning but before early evening due to their home duties)

- FGD materials required:
 - Flipcharts
 - Marker pens
 - (White) masking tape/cellotape, which can also be improvised for nametags
 - Cards (where possible, provide different coloured ones)

Key steps during FGD sessions:

- Seek consent and explain the purpose of the FGD and approximately how long it may take
- Ensure there's balanced participation by drawing in quieter participants and providing them space to talk

Good Practices while conducting FGDs

- Use of recorders (or mobile phone recorders) is encouraged so as to assist note-taker(s) in verbatim recording during FGD sessions. However, the facilitator needs to seek permission from FGD participants for recording.
- To enhance documentation of the 'why' responses on the voting cards by all participants (especially as some may be illiterate or others may find it difficult to express in words reasons for their preferences), prior arrangements need to be made for different field staff to be positioned at different corners where small groups of participants queue up for their responses to be recorded by field staff. Please note that this may take about 30 minutes.
- To ensure FGDs that are within expected time limits, likely delays and recommended time saving strategies are explained below:
 - Language issue that leads to longer translation time: if staff can be trained on conducting FGDs it can take shorter time, and participants can express ideas more easily and in their local language(s).
 - To reduce bias or 'self-answering' when asking FGD questions, it is recommended that non-breeders be trained and engaged as FGD facilitators.
 - If more staff are trained to conduct the separate men and women FGDs simultaneously, this will greatly reduce time needed on a certain day.
 - Same team throughout the FGD sessions would ensure better flow – note taker, translator etc.

FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSION GUIDE

This section consists of:

- Pre-FGD participant registration form
- Oral informed consent (5minutes)
- Introduction/welcome (5minutes)
- Engagement questions (10 minutes)
- Exploration questions (20 minutes)
- Exit questions (10 minutes)
- Review and closing by summarizing key points and thanking participants (10 minutes)

An example of a consent (led by Facilitator)

“Good morning/afternoon everyone, my name is..... and I will be taking you through the discussion for today. The reason for inviting you here today is because we would like to better understand your choices of rice varieties that you have just evaluated. This is part of a project by IRRI country office that is looking into how the rice varieties being developed will meet the needs of both men and women rice farmers in this area.”

(All other staff present introduce themselves, stating their names, IRRI role and their FGD roles for the day (e.g. note-taker, logistical support etc).

“All the information you share with us will be confidential. It will only be shared with our supervisors and work colleagues should they require some further clarifications and discussions. No specific names will be included in the final report. The interview will take about one hour and participation is voluntary, so you may choose either to take part in it or not. If you allow us, will write down some notes so that we can refer to them later on as we write the final report. Is this okay? Could one of our colleagues take photos during the session?”

“Feel free to ask me (or any member of the team) any questions at any time regarding this exercise that may not be clear to you. Do you have any questions now?”

“Can we continue with the group discussion?”
No..... Yes.....

If ‘No’, why?.....

If ‘Yes’, Proceed to “C. Introduction/Welcome” section”

A. Pre-FGD participant registration form
Before the FGD sessions commence, the note-taker needs to fill in a registration form capturing each participant’s basic info and signed consent.

- B. Oral informed consent**
- Number code
 - Participant name
 - Rice area (local unit, please specify)
 - Age (years)
 - Signature (for consenting participant)

Overview

- Greetings and explain what this exercise is about
- Introduce the team members and their roles
- Emphasise anonymity of information will be provided
- Participation is voluntary
- Invite any general questions
- Confirm if women/men willing to participate

C. Introduction/Welcome
[Goal: To help to make the group feel comfortable and let them know what to expect.]

Allow the participants in the group to briefly tell you something about themselves

- Name
- How long have they been growing rice?
 - Thank the participants for coming and tell them they were chosen because they are knowledgeable about the community and can help us understand rice trait preferences in this area.
 - Explain the basic schedule of FGD session (eg the remaining part of our discussion has four parts: engagement, exploration, exit and closing questions)
 - Explain the ground rules:
 - Tell the women/men that they should feel comfortable speaking, that it is okay to disagree and that there are no right or wrong answers
 - We speak one person at a time – when one person speaks the rest keep quiet to listen

D. Engagement Questions
[For this section, the note-taker fills the below questionnaire section as the FGD progresses]

Rice variety	Ranking on preferred rice varieties:
	1 - least preferred
	2 - mid preferred
	3 - most preferred

- From the varietal evaluation you have just participated in, what is the rice variety you prefer most? [Facilitator asks each participant in turn, and lists down the varieties mentioned on a flipchart.

Refer to the extra cards filled during the PVS stage, especially when less than 3 rice varieties are mentioned by all participants]

- From this list, let’s rank the top 3 preferred rice varieties, if more than 3 are evaluated during the PVS [By using cards or raising their hands for each variety mentioned, count the number of farmers preferring each variety, and **note-taker records the counts in the second column of table**]

After the activity, the facilitator presents results to group members and asks if they agree with the results. If more than 3 varieties are evaluated during the PVS, facilitator mentions that for the sake of time, we will only focus on the top three rice varieties per group and we understand they may or may not be an individual’s most preferred rice varieties, which is ok as we need both sets of feedback.]

E. Exploration Questions
[For this section, the note-taker fills the below questionnaire section as the FGD progresses]

- What are the 3 traits you like most about the variety? [Facilitator discusses each variety in turn. Allow each participant to explain why, also probe more on the ‘whys’ in case of one-word response. Facilitator lists down the main points coming up. **Note-taker writes down all these differing opinions verbatim, in respective table rows as appropriate**]
- What are the 3 traits you do not like about the variety? [Facilitator discusses each variety in turn. Allow each participant to explain why, also probe more on the ‘whys’ in case of one-word response. Facilitator lists down the main points coming up. **Note-taker writes down all these differing opinions verbatim, in respective table rows as appropriate**]

[For questions 5-8, note-taker fills below questionnaire section]

- Where do you get information about new rice varieties?
- Are new rice varieties easily accessible? [Facilitator counts the number of ‘yes’ and ‘no’ by asking participants to raise their hands. **Note-taker records the ‘yes’ and ‘no’ counts**]
- Where do you access these new rice varieties?
- Do you change rice varieties often? [Facilitator counts the number of ‘yes’ and ‘no’ by asking participants to raise their hands. Note-taker records the ‘yes’ and ‘no’ counts]
 - For those saying yes, what drives you to change rice varieties?

- For those saying no, why do you not change rice varieties often?

F. Exit questions
[For questions 9-12, note-taker fills below questionnaire section below]

- Can you access the seed of the varieties you want easily when required?
 - Facilitator counts the number of ‘yes’ and ‘no’ by asking participants to raise their hands **[Note-taker records the ‘yes’ and ‘no’ counts]**
- What is the major source of rice seeds that you use?
- If mostly their own seed from the previous crop, how often do you replace the seed?
- If buying:
 - How often do you buy?
 - How much does it cost?
 - Is this price affordable? [Facilitator counts the number of ‘yes’ and ‘no’ by asking participants to raise their hands. **Note-taker records the ‘yes’ and ‘no’ counts**]
 - Are you willing to pay for good quality seed? [Facilitator counts the number of ‘yes’ and ‘no’ by asking participants to raise their hands. **Note-taker records the ‘yes’ and ‘no’ counts**]

[Note-taker fills below responses in the Q & A session]

- As we close, do you have any questions for us?

G. Review and closing

- Facilitator summarises key take-home messages on the top three rice varieties
- Facilitator closes session..see example of closing remarks:

An example of a closing (led by Facilitator)

“I would like to thank you very much for your time and your valuable input. The information you have shared with us will help us to understand how to better release rice varieties that match the diversity of needs existing in this community. As we conclude, would you be okay if we took one group photo? This will help us to remember certain issues if we have a photo in front us...”

(If consent provided, take a group photo of all the group members)

“At this point, I would like to conclude the session. I invite our logistics team to advise us on next steps.”

Download templates here:
bit.ly/genderresponsivecropbreeding

PARTICIPATORY VARIETAL SELECTION (PVS)

Breeding programs produce and evaluate many varieties year after year. These varieties may produce high yield in trials on the research station, but sometimes do not perform well in farmers fields, or may lack a quality trait that is important to farmers. PVS is a simple way for breeders and agronomists to learn which varieties perform well on-farm and are preferred by farmers. Introducing PVS into a variety development program can increase the chances that its products will be adopted.

The mother trial under PVS is an on-farm trial in which a set of new lines or introduced varieties is compared with

local checks using farmers crop management practices. In this step, agronomists measure yield and other important traits. Groups of farmers are invited to visit the trial and rate the varieties using a simple technique called preference analysis (PS). The mother trial does not have to be a separate trial given that name. If the breeding program already conducts researcher-managed on-farm trials, demonstration trials in which data are collected, or even advanced on-station multi-location trials at several research centers, farmers can be invited to visit the trial site and perform PA.

PREFERENCE EVALUATION OF PVS

Guide to the questionnaire

This questionnaire consists of two parts:

Part 1: Varietal evaluation form

A. Basic details of the varieties displayed

- | | |
|---|---|
| a. Date | (Phone number and/or email) |
| b. Start time | |
| c. End time | g. Country |
| d. Name of supervising officer | h. Region |
| e. Job title of supervising officer | i. District |
| f. Contact details of supervising officer | j. Village |
| | k. Station/Ward/Block/any other place description |

II. Variety scoring and scoring rationale: provides room for sex-disaggregated scores for the rice varieties being evaluated, and the reasons for the scoring

- | | |
|-------------------------|-------------------------|
| a. Variety name | c. Women (N = x) |
| b. Men (N = x) | • No. of positive votes |
| • No. of positive votes | • No. of negative votes |
| • No. of negative votes | |

B. Farmers' evaluation form

I. Farmers' data: contains basic socio-economic and demographic characteristics of the participating farmers

- | | |
|---|---|
| a. Number code | monogamous, 2 |
| b. Sex (F/M) | - currently married/ |
| c. Ethnicity/caste (if sensitive, do not ask) | polygamous, 3 - widowed, 4 - divorced, 5 - single) |
| d. Age (years) | h. Size of land owned (local unit, please specify) |
| e. Highest education level (1 - None, 2 - Primary, 3 - Secondary, 4 - Higher) | i. Rice area (local unit, please specify) 2 - Primary, 3 - Secondary, 4 - |
| f. Marital status (1 - currently married/ | |

- | | |
|-------------------------|-----------------------------|
| d. Total (N= x) | f. Main reason(s) for score |
| • No. of positive votes | |
| • No. of negative votes | |
| e. Preference score | |

C. Other stakeholders' evaluation form: Takes into account the presence of a diversity of other stakeholders eg breeders, seed dealers etc.

Variety scoring and scoring rationale: provides room for sex-disaggregated scores, and the reasons for the scoring

- | | |
|---|-----------------------------|
| a. Variety name | • No. of positive votes |
| b. Stakeholder type (e.g. breeder, seed dealer, etc.) | • No. of negative votes |
| c. Men (N = x) | e. Total (N= x) |
| • No. of positive votes | • No. of positive votes |
| • No. of negative votes | f. Preference score |
| d. Women (N = x) | g. Main reason(s) for score |

PVS qualitative data materials:

- Cards
 - For all participants: positive and negative score counts - usually red for negative scores, green for positive scores). Field team needs to collect cards at the end of the PVS exercise.
 - For FGD session participants (Part 2 below)- field team gives an extra card to the selected farmers to indicate top 3 preferred rice varieties (to be used for FGD question 1, page).
- Pens (for writing score rationale on back of the card among the literate participants, while illiterate ones will be assisted by field team members)

Part 2: Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) with separate men and women groups

These gender-specific FGDs are designed to elicit detailed qualitative information underlying varietal scores and preferences. FGD participant recruiters need to:

- Aim for about 6-8 participants (keeping in mind the additional translation time in some contexts)
- To enhance a diversity of participants are invited, the pre-FGD participant registration form captures some socio-economic variation (which can be shared beforehand with personnel assisting with participant recruitment)
- Please ensure timeslots when men and women are invited to participate are when their other time demands are likely to be lower, according to the local area norms (eg in most rural areas, most women farmers may be more available after mid-morning but before early evening due to their home duties)
- FGD materials required:
 - Flipcharts
 - markers pens
 - (White) masking tape/cellotape, which can also be improvised for name tags
 - Cards (where possible, provide different coloured ones)
 - Recorders (if unavailable, mobile phone recorders can also be used)

To enable parts (A) and (B) correspond to the same respondent during data collection, ensure same number code is used for parts (A) and (B), so that both parts of

the results refer to the same person. To further ensure the entries are attributed to the same respondent, the first few column entries for parts (A) and (B) are similar.

Key steps during FGD sessions:

- Seek consent and explain the purpose of the FGD and approximately how long it may take
- Ensure there's balanced participation by drawing in quieter participants and providing them space to talk

Good practices:

- We highly recommend conducting a formal feedback session after the PVS day with all participating staff (social scientists, breeders etc) so as to reflect on what went well and improvement opportunities. Lessons learnt should be documented for cross-learning purposes.
- Use of recorders (or mobile phone recorders) is encouraged so as to assist note-taker(s) in verbatim recording during FGD sessions. However, the facilitator needs to seek permission from FGD participants for recording.
- To enhance documentation of the 'why' responses on the voting cards by all participants (especially as some may be illiterate or others may find it difficult to express in words reasons for their preferences), prior arrangements need to be made for different field staff to be positioned at different corners where small groups of participants queue up for their responses to be recorded by field staff. Please note that this may take about 30 minutes.
- To ensure FGDs that are within expected time limits, likely delays and recommended time saving strategies are explained below:
 - Language issue that leads to longer translation time: if staff can be trained on conducting FGDs it can take shorter time, and participants can express ideas more easily and in their local language(s). And anyone can conduct FGDs, especially if questions are prepared beforehand, and minimal training is provided (furthermore, farmer FGDs are essentially discussions with farmers which most staff already undertake) – to reduce bias or 'self-answering' when asking FGD questions, it is recommended that non-breeders be trained as FGD facilitators.
 - If more staff are trained to conduct the separate men and women FGDs simultaneously, which will greatly reduce field time.
 - Logistics delay: in some PVS events, uniformly labeled attire (t-shirts and caps) are provided to participants – logistical delays in this, and other protocol aspects, further delays the PVS start time – and in turn, the rest of the program, including the FGD sessions. The solutions are:
 - Plan better beforehand: start on time, have other activities that men or women can be doing while doing FGDs (early lunch, individual 'why' questions etc)
 - Same team throughout the FGD sessions would ensure better flow – notetaker, translator, etc.

FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSION GUIDE

This section consists of:

- Pre-FGD participant registration form
- Oral informed consent (5minutes)
- Introduction/welcome (5minutes)
- Engagement questions (10 minutes)
- Exploration questions (20 minutes)
- Exit questions (10 minutes)
- Review and closing by summarizing key points and thanking participants (10 minutes)

An example of a consent (led by Facilitator)

“Good morning/afternoon everyone, my name is..... and I will be taking you through the discussion for today. The reason for inviting you here today is because we would like to better understand your choices of rice varieties that you have just evaluated. This is part of a project by IRRI country office that is looking into how the rice varieties being developed will meet the needs of both men and women rice farmers in this area.”

(All other staff present introduce themselves, stating their names, IRRI role and their FGD roles for the day (e.g. note-taker, logistical support etc).

“All the information you share with us will be confidential. It will only be shared with our supervisors and work colleagues should they require some further clarifications and discussions. No specific names will be included in the final report. The interview will take about one hour and participation is voluntary, so you may choose either to take part in it or not. If you allow us, will write down some notes so that we can refer to them later on as we write the final report. Is this okay? Could one of our colleagues take photos during the session?”

“Feel free to ask me (or any member of the team) any questions at any time regarding this exercise that may not be clear to you. Do you have any questions now?”

“Can we continue with the group discussion?”
No..... Yes.....

If ‘No’, why?.....
...

If ‘Yes’, Proceed to “C. Introduction/Welcome” section’

A. Pre-FGD participant registration form

Before the FGD sessions commence, the note-taker needs to fill in a registration form capturing each participant’s basic info and signed consent.

B. Oral informed consent

- Number code
- Participant name
- Rice area (local unit, please specify)
- Age (years)
- Signature (for consenting participant)

Overview

- Greetings and explain what this exercise is about
- Introduce the team members and their roles
- Emphasise anonymity of information will be provided
- Participation is voluntary
- Invite any general questions
- Confirm if women/men willing to participate

C. Introduction/Welcome

[Goal: To help to make the group feel comfortable and let them know what to expect.]

Allow the participants in the group to briefly tell you something about themselves

- Name
- How long have they been growing rice?
 - Thank the participants for coming and tell them they were chosen because they are knowledgeable about the community and can help us understand rice trait preferences in this area.
 - Explain the basic schedule of FGD session (eg the remaining part of our discussion has four parts: engagement, exploration, exit and closing questions)
 - Explain the ground rules:
 - Tell the women/men that they should feel comfortable speaking, that it is okay to disagree and that there are no right or wrong answers
 - We speak one person at a time – when one person speaks the rest keep quiet to listen

D. Engagement Questions

[For this section, the note-taker fills the below questionnaire section as the FGD progresses]

Rice variety	Ranking on preferred rice varieties:
	1 - least preferred
	2 - mid preferred
	3 - most preferred

- From the varietal evaluation you have just participated in, what is the rice variety you prefer most? [Facilitator asks each participant in turn, and lists down the

varieties mentioned on a flipchart. Refer to the extra cards filled during the PVS stage, especially when less than 3 rice varieties are mentioned by all participants]

- From this list, let’s rank the top 3 preferred rice varieties, if more than 3 are evaluated during the PVS [By using cards or raising their hands for each variety mentioned, count the number of farmers preferring each variety, and note-taker records the counts in the second column of table]

After the activity, the facilitator presents results to group members and asks if they agree with the results. If more than 3 varieties are evaluated during the PVS, facilitator mentions that for the sake of time, we will only focus on the top three rice varieties per group and we understand they may or may not be an individual’s most preferred rice varieties, which is ok as we need both sets of feedback.]

E. Exploration Questions

[For this section, the note-taker fills the below questionnaire section as the FGD progresses]

- What are the 3 traits you like most about the variety? [Facilitator discusses each variety in turn. Allow each participant to explain why, also probe more on the ‘whys’ in case of one-word response. Facilitator lists down the main points coming up. **Note-taker writes down all these differing opinions verbatim, in respective table rows as appropriate]**
- What are the 3 traits you do not like about the variety? [Facilitator discusses each variety in turn. Allow each participant to explain why, also probe more on the ‘whys’ in case of one-word response. Facilitator lists down the main points coming up. **Note-taker writes down all these differing opinions verbatim, in respective table rows as appropriate]**

[For questions 5-7, note-taker fills below questionnaire section]

- Where do you get information about new rice varieties?
- Are new rice varieties easily accessible? [Facilitator counts the number of ‘yes’ and ‘no’ by asking participants to raise their hands. **Note-taker records the ‘yes’ and ‘no’ counts]**
- Where do you access these new rice varieties?
- Do you change rice varieties often? [Facilitator counts the number of ‘yes’ and ‘no’ by asking participants to raise their hands. Note-taker records the ‘yes’ and ‘no’ counts]

- For those saying yes, what drives you to change rice varieties?
- For those saying no, why do you not change rice varieties often?

F. Exit questions

[For questions 8-9, note-taker fills below questionnaire section below]

- Can you access the seed of the varieties you want easily when required?
 - Facilitator counts the number of ‘yes’ and ‘no’ by asking participants to raise their hands **[Note-taker records the ‘yes’ and ‘no’ counts]**
- What is the major source of rice seeds that you use?
- If mostly their own seed from the previous crop, how often do you replace the seed?
- If buying:
 - How often do you buy?
 - How much does it cost?
 - Is this price affordable? [Facilitator counts the number of ‘yes’ and ‘no’ by asking participants to raise their hands. **Note-taker records the ‘yes’ and ‘no’ counts]**
 - Are you willing to pay for good quality seed? [Facilitator counts the number of ‘yes’ and ‘no’ by asking participants to raise their hands. **Note-taker records the ‘yes’ and ‘no’ counts]**

[Note-taker fills below responses in the Q & A session]

- As we close, do you have any questions for us?

G. Review and closing

- Facilitator summarises key take-home messages on the top three rice varieties
- Facilitator closes session..see example of closing remarks:

An example of a closing (led by Facilitator)

“I would like to thank you very much for your time and your valuable input. The information you have shared with us will help us to understand how to better release rice varieties that match the diversity of needs existing in this community. As we conclude, would you be okay if we took one group photo? This will help us to remember certain issues if we have a photo in front us...”

(If consent provided, take a group photo of all the group members)

“At this point, I would like to conclude the session. I invite our logistics team to advise us on next steps.”

SENSORY EVALUATION DURING PVS TRIALS

Guide to the questionnaire

This questionnaire consists of two parts:

Part 1: Basic data

This comprises basic details of the trial data: This contains data on the details of the PVS conducted.

- Date
- Start time
- End time
- Name of supervising officer
- Job title of supervising officer
- Contact details of supervising officer (Phone number and/or email address)
- Country
- Region
- District
- Village
- Station/Ward/Block/any other place description

Part 2: Socio-economic data and and sensory data evaluation form

This comprises:

- Individual farmer evaluation form
- Other stakeholders' individual evaluation form

In each of these sections:

- Farmers' data: Contains basic socio-economic and demographic characteristics of the participating farmers
 - Number code
 - Sex (F/M)
 - Ethnicity/caste (if sensitive, do not ask)
 - Age (years)
 - Highest education level (1 - None, 2 - Primary, 3 - Secondary, 4 - Higher)
 - Martial status (1 - currently married/monogamous, 2 - currently married/polygamous, 3 - widowed, 4 - divorced, 5 - single)
 - Household size
 - Number of years growing rice

- Size of land owned (local unit, please specify)
- Rice area (local unit, please specify)
 - Individual sensory evaluation form
 - Number code
 - Sex (F/M)
 - Age (years)
 - Rice variety name
 - Is this rice variety acceptable to you? Yes/No
 - Why / Why not?
 - Please rank the preference (1=most preferred; 2= mid preferred; 3= least preferred)
 - Why have you given it this rank, based on rice traits (e.g. aroma, colour, taste, gloss, softness etc.)
 - Ask what is it about that trait, and direction of preference (eg if aroma – what about it? Do you want more or less aroma?)
 - What else would you like to see in this rice variety?

To enable parts (i) and (ii) to correspond to the same respondent during data collection, ensure the same number code is used for parts (i) and (ii), so that both parts of the results refer to the same person. To further ensure the entries are attributed to the same respondent, the first few column entries for parts (i) and (ii) are similar.

Download templates here:
bit.ly/genderresponsivecroppbreeding

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International Rice Research Institute

IRRI aims to improve livelihoods and nutrition, abolishing poverty, hunger, and malnutrition among those who depend on rice-based agri-food systems. In doing so, IRRI's work protects the health of rice farmers and consumers, and the environmental sustainability of rice farming in a world challenged by climate change. IRRI's work promotes the empowerment of women and supports opportunities for youth in an equitable agri-food system.

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